

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

APPLICATION OF THE NON-INTERRUPTIBILITY EQUATION TO THE CRYSTAL GROWING PROCESS

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Abstract

The extremely high level of science and technology has been achieved as a result of the rapid development of solid state electronics and construction technology in the last 50 years. This level of development, which is related to the development of semiconductor physics, continues to increase. Even so, the solution of a number of complex issues, which at first seemed like a dream, becomes unbelievably easier. The implementation of computerization in all areas of human activity can be a vivid example of this.

The perfect solution of solid solvent monocrystals can enhance the quality of the devices produced in contemporary solid state electronics. A new method for obtaining monocrystals of binary solutions with strong segregation during crystallization has been proposed. The application of the continuity equation for the growth of single crystals led to the simplification of the case.

Keywords: crystal, growth, semiconductor, component, process.

Introduction

Modern high level of science and technology has been achieved thanks to the rapid development of technology of solid state electronics. The level of development associated with the development of semiconductor physics continues to increase. Thus, it is incredibly easy to solve a number of complicated issues, which previously seemed like a dream. Computerization in all areas of human activity can also be a good example of this.

The vast majority of solid solutions known to date have strong segregation during crystallization. The difficulties in obtaining the mono crystals of such binary solids are known. To achieve the perfect mono crystal, it is desirable to overcome those difficulties. The general principles of the possibility of eliminating the constitutional extreme delusions are known [1, 2]. But these principles can be practiced in different ways. In the article, its optimal variant has been developed and

interpreted. Studies have been carried out by examining the solutions of the intrinsic equilibrium conforming to the specific crystallization conditions at various initial conditions.

Experimental procedure

Firstly, we use the non-intensity equation for the process of growth the monocrystal by extruding the alloy with the application of the binary solids solution. The nutritional, grown crystal and alloy parameters will be shown in accordance with the indexes 1, 2 and 3 respectively. During the t feeding period, the total amount of $V_1(t)$, the volume of the cultured ripened crystals $V_2(t)$, the amount of the alloy in the tube $V_3(t)$, the second component in the nutrient, crystal and allene concentration, $C_2(t)$, and $C_3(t)$, with the first distribution component of the second component k .

The scheme of the monocrystalline breeding process with the application of the nutrient is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Monocrystal growth scheme using nutritional.

Ensuring the uniformity of the alloy (second condition) ensures that the alloy and the crystal are shifted in the opposite direction and the fluid velocity of Ge and Si is very large. The saturated vapor pressure in Ge and Si at $\sim 1000^\circ\text{C}$ is 10^{-5} - 10^{-7} mmHg. It follows

from this that the third condition is also paid in precision.

After considering these, we find the amount of matter of the second component collected in the pot during t :

$$V_3(t)C_3(t) - V_3(0)C_3(0) = \int_0^t \dot{V}_1(t)C_1(t)dt - \int_0^t \dot{V}_2(t)C_2(t)dt \quad (1)$$

here, on the left side of the equilibrium, the amount of the second ingredient in the first charge is the amount of the second ingredient, the second amount at $t = 0$, the amount of the first component at the right

side of the equalizer, the amount of the second component in the alloy, quantity. In order to get the second intake of the substance of the fertility equation, let us derive one time by both times (1):

$$V_3(t)\dot{C}_3(t) + \dot{V}_3(t)C_3(t) = \dot{V}_1(t)C_1(t) - \dot{V}_2(t)C_2(t) \quad (2)$$

According to the definition of the distribution coefficient:

$$k = \frac{C_2(t)}{C_3(t)} \text{ vs } C_2(t) = kC_3(t) \quad (3)$$

Consider (3) in the (2) and group it according to $C(t)$:

$$V_3(t)\dot{C}_3(t) + (\dot{V}_3(t) + k\dot{V}_2(t))C_3(t) = \dot{V}_1(t)C_1(t)$$

Divide both sides into $V_3(t)$:

$$\dot{C}_3(t) + \frac{\dot{V}_3(t) + k\dot{V}_2(t)}{V_3(t)}C_3(t) = \frac{\dot{V}_1(t)C_1(t)}{V_3(t)} \quad (4)$$

To simplify of expression, let us take this substitute:

$$P(t) = \frac{\dot{V}_3(t) + k\dot{V}_2(t)}{V_3(t)}; \quad Q(t) = \frac{\dot{V}_1(t)}{V_3(t)}C_1(t) \quad (5)$$

Should be used (5) – in the (4):

$$\dot{C}_3(t) + P(t)C_3(t) = Q(t) \quad (6)$$

Thus, in the crystallization process, we have acquired the equation that describes the intensity of the substance in the second component. It is an equilateral linear differential equation and its general solution is [3]:

$$C_3(t) = \exp[-\int P(t)dt] \left\{ \int Q(t) \exp[\int P(t)dt] dt + A \right\} \quad (7)$$

Here is the A-decay constant. Its price is determined by the use of the initial conditions for a specific case.

In the crystal growth process, generally using three kinds of geometric formulas, such as semiconductor, shingle cone and cylinder. This often depends on the way in which the material of the potter permits. For example, it is simpler than graphite to make a cone and a cylinder. From the glass and quartz it is possible to put pots on all three geometric structures. The selection of the lubricant material is determined by its purity rate and neutrality against alloy. In the present case, we have taken a transparent quartz form in the form of a semiconductor. The main reason for this is that such a structure has a larger symmetry. In this structure, the temperature of the alloy also has high symmetry, thereby creating more favorable conditions for the production of monocrystals.

In this case, the general scheme of crystallization is as in Figure 1, unless we take into account the initial stage. However, when starting crystallization, it should be taken into consideration that the percentage of the second component in the alloy should gradually increase from zero. Crystallization should be carried out in at least two modes. The easiest way to pay for this condition is to choose a nourishing gel with two different geometrical shapes. If the first part (its beginning) is selected in the form of a cone or rotation

paraboloid, then the concentration of the second component will gradually increase from zero. The second part of the nourishing whitening should be selected so that the concentration of the second component in the pot is kept constant. It is enough to take the second part as a cylinder. At this time, it is possible to choose the shape and size of monocrystals grown. But in the crystallization process, it is more convenient for the stability of the regime to match the shape and dimensions of the crystal with the nourishing xylite. Therefore, the geometrical structure of the crystal is taken in the same manner as the feeder when it does not prevent the intended purpose. For the first regime we will do the same. It should be noted that, in this case, the solution of the intolerance equation is considerably simplified.

So, in the first mode, we get a half, nourishing gel and a grown crystal cone. Since the first regimen is actually a preparatory stage to achieving a stable state of crystal reproduction, there is no need to choose different nutrient speeds and crystal displacement rates.

In the second mode, it is a nourishing crystal, as well as a grown crystal cylinder. However, their diameter and displacement rates are generally different. This condition can be summarized more generally:

$$S_1 v_1 \neq S_2 v_2 \quad (8)$$

Here are three situations: a) $C_1 v_1 = C_2 v_2$;

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{6) } C_1v_1 < C_2v_2 ; \\ & \text{B) } C_1v_1 > C_2v_2 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In this case, the amount of substance from the solid alloy in the solid phase through the crystal trapping is greater than the amount of substance that comes from the nutritive whole. Therefore, as the volume of crystals grows, the amount of substance in the deck will decrease, which means that the surface of the solid alloy will gradually fall. Obviously, in this case, it is necessary to get a lot of pockets to grow big crystals. The nutrient volume should also be selected accordingly.

As the surface of the melt moves, the velocity of the feeding bucket to the alloy is smaller than the velocity of the engine (mechanical engine speed), and the speed of the crystal fluid from the surface of the fluid will be higher than the speed of the stump. If we point to the velocity of the liquid surface relative to the surface 3, relative velocity of the crystal + relative velocity of the nutrient to the surface of the alloy will be 1 - 3.

The cross-section with the vertical diameter of the decanter in the half-shaped figure is shown in Figure 2. After the set t time has elapsed, the current height of the initial volume of the alloy will be reduced to H, and the current radius of the lower seat will be reduced to the size of the spin column. It is clear from the figure that the speed of the liquid surface is not stable. As we look, it grows dependent on time. Obviously, this action will be very small, and the 3 most recent final price will be smaller than 1 and 2. We can find that the exact expression of the motion of the surface of the alloy is equal to the change in the mass of the whole mass of the alloy in the powder crystal with the feeding mass of the mass. However, this is a very complicated issue, and the result obtained here makes it difficult for the integration of the solution of the intolerance problem. Therefore, we will choose a simple path here. Since the price of the momentum is stable, we can assign it at any point to the price of the road and time. At such a point, we can choose the moment when the process is over. Let's point out the value of t₂ and H with H_{max} at the moment of matching. Since this process occurs after the time t₁, we can write the expression of H_{max}:

$$H_{\max} = v_3(t_1)(t_2 - t_1) + \frac{a(t_2 - t_1)^2}{2} = \frac{a(t_2 - t_1)^2}{2} \quad (10)$$

Here v_{3(t₁)} – s the starting speed of the melt movement in this process. Consider that it is zero. v₃ the average price for changing the line, v̄₃ according to the starting point and the end points:

$$\bar{v}_3 = \frac{v_3(t_1) + v_3(t_2)}{2} = \frac{0 + a(t_2 - t_1)}{2} = \frac{a(t_2 - t_1)}{2} \quad (11)$$

So, we'll use the average of 3 in the calculations. Write appropriate volumes:
$$\left. \begin{aligned} V_1(t) &= S_1(v_1 - \bar{v}_3)t' \\ V_2(t) &= S_2(v_2 + \bar{v}_3)t' \end{aligned} \right|$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} V_3(t) &= V_3(0) - \Delta V \\ t' &= t - t_1 \end{aligned} \right| \quad (12)$$

In the last formula ΔB – posea t is the size of the spatial zone formed between its t1 at t at the t as a result of the reduction of the alloy during t (Figure 2). This volume can be found in geometric ways. But the most advantageous is finding it as V₁ with V₂.

Figure 2. The diameter of the platoon in the form of a half-shaped cut, with the cross-section through the diameter of the platen.

For the case we look at P(t) and (Q(t) parameters write down clearly:

$$P(t) = \frac{\dot{V}_3 + k\dot{V}_2}{V_3} = \frac{S_2k(v_2 + \bar{v}_3) - \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_m} (S_2(v_2 + \bar{v}_3) - S_1(v_1 - \bar{v}_3))}{V_3(0) - \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_m} [S_2(v_2 + \bar{v}_3) - S_1(v_1 - \bar{v}_3)]t'} \quad (13)$$

$$Q(t) = \frac{\dot{V}_1(t)}{V_3(t)} C_1(t) = \frac{S_1(v_1 - \bar{v}_3) C_1}{V_3(0) - \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_m} [S_2(v_2 + \bar{v}_3) - S_1(v_1 - \bar{v}_3)] t'} \quad (14)$$

$C_1(t) = C_1 = \text{const.}$

(13) and (14) Instead, we have to write in the general solution of the intrinsic equation (7) and after some mathematical calculations:

$$C_2(t) = \begin{cases} C_1 \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{kV_k}{V_3(0)} \cdot \frac{t^3}{t_1^3}\right) \right], & 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \\ \frac{a_2}{a_1} + k \left\{ \frac{C_1}{k} \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{kV_k}{V_3(0)}\right) \right] - \frac{a_2}{a_1} \right\} \cdot \left(\frac{V_3(0) - \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_m} [S_2(v_2 + \bar{v}_3) - S_1(v_1 - \bar{v}_3)] t'}{V_3(0)} \right)^{\frac{kS_2(v_2 + \bar{v}_3) - \frac{\rho_b}{\rho_m} (S_2(v_2 + \bar{v}_3) - S_1(v_1 - \bar{v}_3))}{\frac{\rho_b}{\rho_m} [S_2(v_2 - v_3) - S_1(v_1 - \bar{v}_3)]}}, & t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

a_1, a_2 – known constants.

In the (15) the relative distribution for the Ge-Si system is shown in Figure 3(1 curve).

Figure 3. Relative distribution of the composition throughout the crystal (1 curve) according to (3.55).

Result. The main point here is that the concentration of the second component is less than the value of its nutritional alloy, so that the crystallization regime can be upgraded with the same concentration of the second component by means of the same nutritional xylite as the solid crystal monocrystals with a smaller content than the nourishing halide.

References

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